

The Role of Women in the Upanishads: A Philosophical Inquiry into Gender and Spirituality

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the portrayal of women in the Upanishads, exploring their philosophical and spiritual roles in ancient Indian thought. Focusing on key figures such as Maitreyī, Kātyāyanī, and Gārgī, the study highlights how women were integral to the discourse on the Ātman (soul) and the pursuit of immortality. The Upanishads, revered for their metaphysical insights, present women not merely as complements to men but as active participants in philosophical debates and spiritual practices. Through an examination of dialogues such as those between Yājñavalkya and Maitreyī, the paper uncovers the elevated status accorded to women, their quest for knowledge, and their contribution to the understanding of Brahman. This analysis challenges modern perceptions of gender roles in ancient texts, revealing a nuanced and respectful approach to women's intellectual and spiritual capabilities in the Upanishadic tradition.

Keywords: Women and Upanishads; Gender and Scholarship; Gender and Spirituality.

In the Upanishads, we encounter two remarkable women who could engage in profound philosophical discussions, even with the great sage Yājñavalkya. One of these women was his wife, Maitreyī, and the other was his intellectual adversary, Gārgī, the daughter of the sage Vachaknu. This paper focuses on Maitreyī, as she is portrayed in the Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad. We will briefly explore the role of women in the Upanishads, introduce Maitreyī and her philosophical inquiry, and examine her conversation with Yājñavalkya. The Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad is the largest of the eleven existing Upanishads and forms part of the Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa of the White Yajurveda. It is called "Bṛhadāraṇyaka" because it is "Bṛhad" (large) and belongs to the Āraṇyaka section.

The Place of Women in the Upanishads

According to the Upanishads, women were created to complete men. In the beginning, the Ātman (Self) was alone, feeling fear and lacking joy. Desiring companionship, the Ātman became as large as a man and a woman in close embrace, splitting itself into two halves—man and wife. The Upanishads often mention female counterparts in philosophical concepts: Vāk (speech) is considered female, while Prāṇa (breath) is male; their union gives birth to the syllable "Om." The elevated status of women is also apparent in the Chāndogya Upaniṣad, which states that seeing a woman after performing the Mantha rite is a sign that one's efforts have borne fruit.

Women were not seen as unwanted or inferior. The Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad even prescribes a rite for obtaining a long-living and scholarly daughter (Bṛh. Up. VI.4.17). The debate between Yājñavalkya and Gārgī illustrates that women were honored and had the freedom to interact freely with others, engage in debates, and participate in philosophical discussions in assemblies of learned

scholars. Knowledge provided them with status and the ability to assert themselves in intellectual matters.

In the Upaniṣads, we encounter three main types of women: Kātyāyanī, a worldly woman mentioned only once in the Bṛhadāraṇyaka; Maitreyī, a spiritual woman and fitting companion to the philosopher Yājñavalkya; and Gārgī, an intellectual who boldly challenges Yājñavalkya, demonstrating her expertise in philosophical discourse and intellectual debate.

Maitreyī

Maitreyī was the wife of the great sage Yājñavalkya and was familiar with Brahman (spiritual knowledge, or Brahmvādinī). In the Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad, we find the celebrated conversation between Yājñavalkya and Maitreyī when Yājñavalkya intended to divide his estate between his two wives, Kātyāyanī and Maitreyī, before renouncing his householder's life. Yājñavalkya's teachings to Maitreyī revolve around the idea that the Ātman (Self) is the ultimate goal of human life and the reality by knowing which everything is known. Yājñavalkya imparts to Maitreyī that knowledge of Brahman is the means to immortality, forming the highest teaching of the Upaniṣads.

Maitreyī's Philosophical Inquiry

Maitreyī's primary inquiry was to understand the true path to immortality. She asked Yājñavalkya whether even the greatest wealth could make her immortal (amṛta). Maitreyī said, "What shall I do with that which will not make me immortal?" She insisted on receiving spiritual instruction instead of material wealth.

Context of the Dialogue Between Maitreyī and Yājñavalkya

Delighted by her curiosity, Yājñavalkya taught Maitreyī with great tenderness. Their dialogue is considered an exemplary model of dialectics in the Upaniṣadic tradition, with Yājñavalkya declaring that he had decided to end his householder's life and pursue the path of the Absolute in solitude. Maitreyī, however, was not an ordinary woman who would accept such a decision without understanding the value Yājñavalkya saw in the path he was choosing. Realizing that his choice was for immortality and the realization of the highest truth, she also wished to seek the one truth without a second. It is with this understanding that we should approach the dialogue between Yājñavalkya and Maitreyī.

1. Quest for Immortality (Bṛhad. Up. II, 5. verses 1-4)

Here, we see Yājñavalkya preparing to leave his grhastha (householder) āśrama and move to the next stage, sannyāsa (renunciation). Many scholars have underestimated his other wife, Kātyāyanī, by suggesting that she possessed only the knowledge typical of women. However, the Upaniṣad conveys a different message: historically, men were free to wander (as sannyāsins or in the vānaprastha āśrama), while women took care of the household and children. The main responsibility for family upkeep fell, and often still falls, on women. It is a misconception to view Kātyāyanī as inferior to Maitreyī.

The first mantra is better understood by recognizing that Maitreyī was knowledgeable in contemplative disciplines aimed at Self-realization, while Kātyāyanī had a socially responsible mindset, which she maintained for the welfare of the world, including her own family. In the dialogue, Maitreyī's rhetorical question—"Will wealth make me immortal?"—refers to the discipline of not desiring anything in this life or the next. By questioning the value of wealth, Maitreyī seeks to confirm her belief that material wealth is not a substitute for the realization of the Self. This question indicates her willingness to renounce worldly attachments and her deep desire for liberation.

This passage shows that during the Upaniṣadic period, women had the right to express their thoughts and make choices about their spiritual lives and pursuits. Maitreyī's inquiry reveals that she likely had some prior education or knowledge beyond worldly pleasures. Her question contributes to humanity's understanding that wealth and rituals performed with wealth cannot lead to immortality.

Accustomed to hearing masculine perspectives, we are now struck by Maitreyī, a woman, voicing a message as profound and solemn as any other in our world of thought. This search for immortality is key to understanding one's lifelong spiritual practice (sādhana). The quest for immortality must lead to prema (love). Love for the Self, for a knower of Brahman, naturally extends to love for all—humanity, the universe—unrestricted by parochialism or narrowness.

Rabindranath Tagore eloquently stated: "This simple cry by Maitreyī was transformed into a kind of prayer. Has such a complete prayer ever been heard anywhere?" Tagore resonated deeply with Maitreyī's spiritual plea.

In the third mantra, Maitreyī asks about the way to immortality, and Yājñavalkya explains that there is one indivisible Reality that manifests itself in various forms and individualities. This Reality is the Ātman. Complete identification with the Self, which exists within oneself and all, is the way to immortality.

2. Existence of All Beings for the Sake of the Ātman (verses 5-6)

Seeking immortality, Maitreyī rejects worldly riches and implores Yājñavalkya for the means to attain it. Yājñavalkya responds by listing various things in life—husband, wife, children, wealth, the brahmana, the kṣatriya, worlds, gods, and beings—each cherished not for its own sake, but for the sake of the Self. Finally, he states that the Ātman must be realized.

Yājñavalkya explains that the Self should be seen, heard, understood, and meditated upon. When the Self is truly known, all else is known, for nothing is truly understood unless seen about the Self. The Self is a singular, concrete Reality, whereas the so-called realities of the world are mere abstractions. In the seventh mantra, Yājñavalkya says the Self is naturally dear to everyone, and it is the presence of the Self in people and things that make them dear to us.

Here, we see Maitreyī receiving the means to immortality and continuing her spiritual quest. It is clear that Self-realization, as understood by the Upaniṣadic seers, involves the unfolding and realization of the Ātman within. This passage teaches that the Ātman, the ultimate Reality within and without, should be the highest object of desire, surpassing any phenomenal object of love, such as progeny or wealth, because the Ātman is the very core of existence.

3. The World-Soul (Ātman) or Brahman (verses 10-12)

Yājñavalkya tells Maitreyī that when the fire is kindled with wet faggots, various forms of smoke and sparks emerge. He compares these different formations to the four Vedas, history, mythology, arts, Upaniṣads, aphorisms, elucidations, and explanations.

Conclusion:

The Upanishads present a complex and respectful portrayal of women, depicting them as essential partners in the spiritual and philosophical life of society. Figures like Maitreyī and Gārgī demonstrate that women were not only valued for their roles as wives and mothers but also for their intellectual prowess and spiritual insights. The dialogues within these texts highlight the pursuit of immortality as a shared human endeavor, transcending gender. Maitreyī's inquiry into the nature of the Self (Ātman) and her rejection of material wealth in favor of spiritual knowledge underscores the profound respect for women's spiritual aspirations in the Upanishadic tradition. This study concludes that the Upanishads offer a rich and egalitarian perspective on gender, emphasizing the importance of both men and women in the pursuit of ultimate truth and liberation. The philosophical contributions of these women challenge contemporary stereotypes and offer a timeless message about the value of knowledge, regardless of gender.

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